

ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE DRIVEN EVALUATION OF CHANGES IN THE ECOSYSTEM EXTENT IN SRI LANKA (1980–2018): A GATEWAY TO NATURAL CAPITAL VALUATION

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Abstract

Lack of available, reliable and complete data is a problem in natural capital valuation research. The ecosystem valuation data are better suited for natural capital valuation. This study used SEEA EA Artificial Intelligence (AI) driven modeling platform and generated ecosystem extent data to create awareness among researchers. The long-term changes in the extents due to additions and regressions among ecosystems are highlighted

INTRODUCTION

Lack of available, reliable and complete data is a problem in natural capital valuation research. High cost for data collection and application difficulties of conventional data collection tools further aggravated this problem. Therefore, use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) with remote sensing data is becoming popular in this subject. However, awareness about available AI tools and their application is limited in Sri Lanka.

Natural capital valuation employs two main approaches: (i) individual component assessment and (ii) ecosystem assessment. The individual component approach focuses on valuing specific natural resources individually (e.g. soil, forest), while the ecosystem approach considers the complex interactions and services provided by entire ecosystem (Ignatyeva et al., 2020; Baciú et al., 2021). Individual component provides detailed information on specific stocks (e.g. forest, water body), but often overlook interactions among components (Peskest, et.al, 2023, Robi,et.al, 2020). In contrast, ecosystem assessment approach adopts a holistic perspective, where biotic and abiotic components interact to produce ecosystem services. This approach considers the combined extent, condition, and functionality of ecosystems as a whole, capturing interdependencies like nutrient cycling, habitat connectivity, and regulating services that individual component assessments often does not capture (Ignatyeva, et.al,2020, Anne, et.al, 2015). In essence, individual component assessments provide granular, asset-specific data, while ecosystem assessments offer a systemic understanding of natural capital dynamics and ecosystem services flows. Therefore, ecosystem assessment approach is a technically better holistic approach for natural capital valuation. However, availability of data for multivariate indicators and quality of data is a limitation in natural capital valuation research. The solution to this limitation is the application of AI based tools for ecosystem accounting.

Artificial Intelligence for Environment and Sustainability (ARIES), developed by researchers at the Basque Centre for Climate Change-BC3 - is an integrated, open-source modelling platform for environmental sustainability (BC3, 2025). The System of Environmental-Economic Accounting Ecosystem Accounting (SEEA EA) was established under the auspices of the United Nations, specifically through the work of the United Nations Statistical Division (UNSD) and the United Nations Statistical Commission (United Nations et al., 2021). The SEEA is the accepted international statistical standard for environmental-economic accounting, providing a framework for organizing and presenting statistics on the environment and its relationship with the economy. ARIES officially joined and began supporting the UN SEEA EA framework in 2021.

The ARIES SEEA EA is a platform that generates data for five ecosystem accounts, namely, ecosystem extent, ecosystem condition, ecosystem services (physical and monetary) and ecosystem assets. It brings together economic and environmental information in an internationally agreed set of standard concepts, definitions, classifications, accounting rules and tables to produce internationally comparable statistics (SEEA 2025). The SEEA Ecosystem Accounting has been adopted as a global statistical standard for measuring ecosystem extent, condition, and services by machine learning oriented researchers and organization like UN, World Bank and EU- globally - as it helps comparisons at globally, nationally, administrative and by geographic locations. However, information in Figure 1 indicate that ARIES SEEA EA modeling platform has not been implemented in Sri Lanka until July, 2025. It indicates lack of awareness of the AI tool. Data from all SEEA EA accounts are needed for natural capital valuation. Therefore, this study has been designed to generate data and evaluate the long-term changes in the extent of ecosystems of Sri Lanka during 1980-2018 using ARIES SEEA EA modeling platform and (ii) to create awareness among Sri Lankan researchers on potential of ARIES SEEA EA tool in natural capital valuation.

SORURCE: SEEA EA as of July, 2025

Figure1. ARIES SEEA EA is not implemented in white colored countries

METHODOLOGY

This pioneering research used an innovative Artificial Intelligence modeling platform ARIES SEEA EA to evaluate the changes in ecosystem extents in Sri Lanka over 1980-2018 period. Ecosystem accounting area (EAA) is the geographical territory for which an ecosystem account is compiled (SEEA, 2025). In this study, EAA is computed for national level of Sri Lanka. The ARIES SEEA EA system generates data for indicators like landcover, aridity, mean temperature (C), landform and elevation(m) for any geographic area using data available in the system and derive data for relevant indicators of the ecosystem accounts.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The ARIES SEEA EA generated extent accounts for both ecosystems and land cover systems of Sri Lanka. Three data tables related to ecosystem extent and land cover extents each are generated by the system as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Titles of three extent accounts generated by ARIES SEEA EA

Tables for Ecosystem extent accounts	Tables for land cover extent accounts)
Table: Extent account: net balance Table: Extent account: additions and reductions Table: Ecosystem type: change matrix	Table: Land account: Net balance Table: Land account: additions and reductions Table: Land cover type: change matrix

The Table 2 shows that ecosystem categories and land cover categories generated by the machine for Sri Lanka. It is useful to compare the AI-based results with existing knowledge. The information in Table 2 is also useful to understand the types of ecosystems, land covers and forest covers that are focused by ARIES SEEA EA.

Table 2. Types of ecosystems, land covers and forest types for which data are generated by ARIES SEEA EA for Sri Lanka

Ecosystems types	Land covers types	Forest types
Aquatic, Boreal temperate montane forest woodland, Cropland, Intertidal forest shrubland, Rocky pavement lava flow scree, Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland, Seasonally dry tropical shrubland, Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket, Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest, Tropical subtropical montane rainforest, Tropical subtropical savanna, Urban industrial ecosystem, Warm temperate tropical marsh, Unaccounted	Agricultural land with natural vegetation, Artificial surface, Bare area, closed deciduous broadleaf forest, Closed savanna, Complex cultivation patterned land, Deciduous broadleaf forest, Deciduous coniferous forest, Evergreen broadleaf forest, Evergreen coniferous forest, Evergreen shrubland, Grassland, Mangrove, Non-irrigated arable land, herbaceous open savanna, permanently irrigated arable land, Shrubland Sparse vegetation, Water body, Wetland	Boreal temperate montane forest woodland, Temperate forest, Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest, Tropical subtropical montane rainforest, Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket

Ecosystems Extent Account - Net Balance (km²) Between 1980 and 2018 in Sri Lanka

The net balance of extents of 16 ecosystems of Sri Lanka are shown in Table 3. The ecosystems maps of Sri Lanka generated by SEEA EA platform for 1980 and 2018 are shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3 respectively. The ecosystem maps for Sri Lanka (Figure 2) shows 29 ecosystem types. However, SEEA AI platform generates ecosystem extent data only for 16 ecosystems (Table 3) as reference ecosystem types in Sri Lanka.

Ecosystem extent account records the total area of each ecosystem, classified by type within a specified area (ecosystem accounting area). Ecosystem extent accounts are measured over time in ecosystem accounting areas (e.g. nation, province, river basin, protected area, etc.) by

ecosystem type, thus illustrating the changes in extent from one ecosystem type to another over the accounting period. In this research, the ecosystem accounting area is selected as the national level of Sri Lanka. Ecosystem types and land cover types are defined by the IUCN global ecosystem typology 2.0 (Keith, et.al, 2020) that has 48 ecosystem types of which 29 are available in Sri Lanka.

Table 3. Ecosystems Extent Account - Net Balance (km²) Between 1980 and 2018

Indicator	Aquatic	Boreal temperate montane forest woodland	Cropland	Intertidal forest shrubland	Rocky pavement lava flow scree	Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland	Seasonally dry tropical shrubland	Temperate forest	Temperate sub humid grassland	Temperate woodland
Year 1980	33254.04	271.15	30692.26	220.19	82.28	822.72	6433.44	0.37	0.37	77.89
Year 2018	33266.99	270.41	31313.31	240.51	86.35	1022.99	7552.09	0.37	0.37	82.72
Net change	12.95	-0.74	621.04	20.32	4.07	200.27	1118.65	0.00	0.00	4.82

Table 3. Continued

Indicator	Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket	Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest	Tropical subtropical montane rainforest	Tropical subtropical savanna	Urban industrial ecosystem	Warm temperate tropical marsh
Year 1980	2697.05	5681.99	10014.23	6968.68	603.35	0.37
Year 2018	2061.04	3128.62	8016.64	9638.69	1154.09	0.37
Net change	-636.00	-2553.37	-1997.59	2670.01	550.74	0.00

Source: Author generated using SEEA EA

The Ecosystem Extent Maps of Sri Lanka 1980 and 2018

Figure 2. Ecosystem extents of Sri Lanka in 1980 and 2018 -SEEA maps formatted by author

The Pareto chart (Figure 3) shows extents and cumulative percent of ecosystem extents of Sri Lanka in 2018. It indicates that the total extent of ecosystems in Sri Lanka is 97,836 km² and of which aquatic (33,267 km²) and croplands (31,313 km²) are the largest ecosystems and they account for 34% and 32% respectively and for 66% of the total. The 84% of total ecosystem extent is due to aquatic and croplands together with tropical subtropical savanna (10%), and tropical subtropical montane rainforest (8%).

source: Author's own work

Figure 3. Pareto chart showing extent and cumulative percent of ecosystem extents in Sri Lanka in 2018.

Source: created by Author

Figure 4. Pareto chart (without aquatic ecosystem) showing extent and cumulative percent of ecosystem extents in Sri Lanka in 2018.

If we ignore aquatic ecosystem, the share of other ecosystem extents are shown in Figure 4.

The data in Figure 4 indicate that 88% of total ecosystem extent (without aquatic ecosystem) consists of croplands (49%), tropical subtropical savanna (15%), tropical subtropical montane rainforest (12%) and seasonally dry tropical shrubland (12%).

Net Changes in Ecosystem extents (1980-2018)

Source: created by author

Figure 5. Net change in ecosystem extents (sq. km) from 1980 to 2018

Source: created by author

Figure 6. Pareto Chart Showing Magnitude and Cumulative net Change in Extent of Ecosystems (1980-2018)

Net Changes in Ecosystem Extents (1980-2018)

The data in Table 3 and Figure 5 shows that the ecosystems with increased net extents (km²) are tropical subtropical savanna (2670.01), seasonally dry tropical shrubland (1118.65), cropland (621.04), urban industrial ecosystem (550.74), intertidal forest shrubland (20.32), seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland (20.27), aquatic (12.95), temperate woodland (4.82) and rocky pavement lava flow scree (4.07). The ecosystems with large decreased extents (km²) are tropical subtropical dry forest thicket (-636.00), tropical subtropical lowland rainforest (-2553.37), and tropical subtropical montane rainforest (-1997.59). Total extent increased in savanna and shrubland ecosystems is 5202.87 km² and total extent decreased in forest ecosystems is 5186.59 km². Debatably, about 5000 km² dry and rainforest ecosystems have changed into savanna and shrubland ecosystems during 1980-2018 period.

Pareto chart showing magnitude and cumulative change in net extent of ecosystems are shown in Figure 6. Pareto rule is referred as 80/20 rule. Application of this rule to total ecosystem extent change revealed that the about 84.7% of the total extent increased in ecosystems account for three ecosystem types, namely, tropical subtropical savanna (51.3%) and seasonally dry tropical shrubland (21.5%) and Cropland (11.9 %). Increase in Urban-industrial ecosystem (10.5%), Intertidal forest shrubland (4.0%), Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland (3.8%) are also observed.

The data in Table 3 indicate that the savanna (51.3%) and shrubland (29.3%) ecosystem types have increased over the years with decrease in forest types. Savannas are ecosystems characterized by grasses with scattered trees or shrubs. They are typically found in tropical and subtropical regions with seasonal rainfall. Shrublands are areas dominated by low, woody shrubs, often in semi-arid climates. Vegetation is short, dense shrubs, sparse trees, and adapted to drought and fire. Shrublands could be degraded lands where forests have been cleared and didn't fully rederived. This information is useful for environmental management, conservation prioritization, or ecosystem accounting and planning.

Comparison of Results with Existing Knowledge

In order to compare the ecosystem types results produced by ARIES SEEA EA system with existing knowledge, it is necessary to highlight the Sri Lankan ecosystems reported by other sources. It has been noticed that different level of aggregation is used by different sources to group ecosystems. The information in Wikipedia (2025) classify Sri Lankan ecosystems as Terrestrial and Aquatic and then further into 17 ecosystems. The detail ecosystem classifications are reported in Sri Lanka's National Biodiversity Strategic Action Plan 2016–2022 (NBSAP, 2016). This action plan provides an overview of Sri Lanka's ecosystem diversity. It reported six forests, eight grasslands, two caves, five man-made ecosystems, one Lentic (standing) water bodies, two Lotic (running) water bodies, one marshland, four beaches, four shallow marine water (less than 200 m), five deep marine water (more than 200 m) and three islets. This information suggests that altogether 43 ecosystems are present in Sri Lanka. It is worth noting here that these ecosystems are classified considering factors like zoogeographic, topographic, climatic, edaphic factors, and humanmade ecosystems (NBSAP, 2016) and hence they are different from IUCN ecosystems. Another report on Sri Lanka's biodiversity has reported 12 ecosystems (CBD, 2025). The level 3 Ecosystem Functional Groups (EFG) of the IUCN Global Ecosystem Typology 2.0 (Keith et.al, 2020) provide comprehensive global biomes and ecosystem functional groups classification based on functional, environmental and biotic composition characteristics. Therefore, IUCN ecosystems are different from biodiversity-based ecosystems. Nimal et.al (2008) reported eight coastal ecosystems, three inland aquatic systems, six terrestrial-natural forest ecosystems and six natural grassland ecosystems (23 ecosystems) in Sri Lanka.

Change in Ecosystem Extent (Additions and Reductions)

The change in ecosystem extent (additions and reductions) in km² between 1980-2018 is shown in Table 4. The net changes in extent due to additions and regressions from other ecosystems is explained in pairwise comparison Table 5.

On Pairwise Comparison of Ecosystem Extent Change due to additions and regressions (1980-2018)

The ecosystems change matrix (Table 5) explains the conversion of other ecosystems to another ecosystem and derive additions to the second ecosystem. The sum of these converted numbers is equal to the given ecosystem extent shown in Table 3 and Table 4. For example, sum of numbers in tropical subtropical savanna ecosystem, i.e. 9638.69 km² in Table 5 equal to closing area of 2018 for tropical subtropical savanna ecosystem in Table 4 and tropical subtropical savanna ecosystem extent in Table 3.

Pairwise Comparison of Data for Tropical Subtropical Savanna

Savannas and croplands are important ecosystems as they are the result of converged other ecosystems. Both have ecological and socio-economic importance as well.

The pairwise comparison of data (Table 5) for tropical subtropical savanna indicates the extents (km²) of other ecosystems changed to tropical subtropical savanna ecosystem during 1980-2018 (38 years) period. They are aquatic (3.32) cropland (172.99), seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland (14.83), seasonally dry tropical shrubland (73.71), Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket (353.17), tropical subtropical lowland rainforest (1240.28) and tropical subtropical montane rainforest (1055.25) and the total expansion is 2913.58. This number is shown in Table 4 column for tropical subtropical savanna. Examination of data on conversions between different ecosystem types revealed that about 2295.53 km² lowland rainforest and montane rainforests have changed to savanna ecosystems during last 38 years. Savanna ecosystems are dominated by grasses, with scattered trees and sometimes shrubs. The majority of the ground cover in savannas consists of perennial herbaceous plants, mainly C4 grasses, making grasses the dominant vegetation type. By definition, grasslands and savannas can be either anthropogenic or natural. Anthropogenic grasslands and savannas require some form of disturbance, such as cultivation, heavy grazing, burning, or mowing to persist (UNESCO EOLSS, 2025). Figure 3 generated by SEEA EA shows that Savannas are concentrated in the dry zone of Sri Lanka. Does this observation suggest that said disturbances to other ecosystems is high in the Dry Zone? This has to be studied in the future research for confirmation.

Similar interpretation can be made for each ecosystem in Table 5. It is not performed here as it is beyond the scope this research. The forestry and other relevant researches can interpret the data in Table 4 and Table 5 with complementary data from GIS in future research.

The Net Change in Ecosystem Extent (Additions and Reductions) between 1980-2018

Table 4. Ecosystems Extent Account – Additions and Reductions (Km²) Between 1980 and 2018

Indicator	Aquatic	Boreal temperate montane forest woodland	Cropland	Intertidal forest shrubland	Rocky pavement lava flow scree	Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland	Seasonally dry tropical shrubland	Temperate forest	Temperate sub humid grassland
Opening area 1980	33254.04	271.15	30692.26	220.19	82.28	822.72	6433.44	0.37	0.37
Expansions	46.58	26.71	2331.34	25.50	4.80	344.45	1550.18	0.00	0.00
Regressions	33.63	27.45	1710.30	5.18	0.74	66.39	509.33	0.00	0.00
Net change	12.95	-0.74	621.04	20.32	4.07	278.07	1040.86	0.00	0.00
Closing area at start of 2018	33266.99	270.41	31313.31	240.51	86.35	1100.79	7474.30	0.37	0.37

Table 4. Continued

Indicator	Temperate woodland	Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket	Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest	Tropical subtropical montane rainforest	Tropical subtropical savanna	Urban industrial ecosystem	Warm temperate tropical marsh	Unaccounted	Totals
Opening area 1980	77.89	2697.05	5681.99	10014.23	6968.68	603.35	0.37	74.37	97894.76
Expansions	14.47	68.01	97.12	459.19	2913.58	550.74	0.00	3.70	8436.39
Regressions	9.64	704.01	2650.49	2456.78	243.57	0.00	0.00	18.88	8436.39
Net change	4.82	-636.00	-2553.37	-1997.59	2670.01	550.74	0.00	-15.18	0.00
Closing area at start of 2018	82.72	2061.04	3128.62	8016.64	9638.69	1154.09	0.37	59.20	97894.76

Source . ARIES (Artificial Intelligence for Environment & Sustainability) UN SEEA EA

Table 5. Ecosystems Type Change Matrix (Km²) Between 1980 and 2018 by ARIES (Artificial Intelligence for Environment and Sustainability) SEEA EA

Ecosystem	Aquatic	Boreal temperate montane forest woodland	Cropland	Intertidal forest shrubland	Rocky pavement lavaflow scree	Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland	Seasonally dry tropical shrubland	Temperate forest	Temperate subhumid grassland	Temperate woodland	Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket	Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest	Tropical subtropical montane rainforest	Tropical subtropical savanna	Urban industrial ecosystem	Warm temperate tropical marsh	Unaccounted
Aquatic	33220.40	0.00	9.97	8.86	1.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.11	0.00	3.32	7.05	0.00	2.22
Boreal temperate montane forest woodland	0.00	243.70	12.24	0.00	0.00	1.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	11.13	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	2.97	0.00	0.00
Cropland	12.93	13.35	28981.96	15.16	2.59	9.27	703.44	0.00	0.00	2.97	32.50	48.18	255.62	172.99	439.80	0.00	1.48
Intertidal forest shrubland	1.11	0.00	2.22	215.01	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.48	0.00	0.00
Rocky pavement lavaflow scree	0.00	0.00	0.74	0.00	81.55	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Seasonally dry temperate heath shrubland	0.00	6.31	1.48	0.00	0.00	756.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.37	41.91	14.83	1.11	0.00	0.00
Seasonally dry tropical shrubland	0.74	0.00	163.38	0.37	0.00	114.93	5924.11	0.00	0.00	0.00	4.07	33.06	101.24	73.72	17.82	0.00	0.00
Temperate forest	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Temperate subhumid grassland	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Temperate woodland	0.00	7.05	1.48	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	68.25	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.11	0.00	0.00
Tropical subtropical dry forest thicket	0.37	0.00	230.91	0.00	0.00	0.00	119.55	0.00	0.00	0.00	1993.04	0.00	0.00	353.17	0.00	0.00	0.00
Tropical subtropical lowland rainforest	15.19	0.00	1062.23	0.00	0.74	0.00	315.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	3031.50	0.00	1240.28	16.71	0.00	0.00
Tropical subtropical montane rainforest	2.59	0.00	774.24	0.37	0.00	208.75	403.34	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	7557.45	1055.26	12.24	0.00	0.00
Tropical subtropical savanna	9.23	0.00	64.31	0.74	0.00	10.39	8.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	31.43	14.41	60.42	6725.10	44.50	0.00	0.00
Urban industrial ecosystem	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	603.35	0.00	0.00
Warm temperate tropical marsh	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.00
Unaccounted	4.43	0.00	8.14	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	5.94	0.00	55.49

Conclusion

ARIES SEEA EA artificial intelligence modeling platform generate ecosystem extent data for Sri Lanka. These data help analyze long term net changes as well as addition and reductions of ecosystem extents over time. The ARIES SEEA EA AI driven platform can be used for natural capital valuation reserach.

A general trend of changing forest ecosystem to savanna and shrubland is observed in the data. The ecological, environmental and monetary impact of these changes needs to be investigated in future research

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